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UPWARDS

Deliverable D6.1

Serial Integrated Simulation Platform

WP	6	Integrated System Simulation and Knowledge Extraction
Task	6.1	Serial Integrated Simulation Platform provided to partner

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public. **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU). **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU). **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

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Deliverable abstract

This documents reports about the **Serial Integrated Simulation Platform**, which we implemented in Task 6.1 and delivered to the partners of the Upwards consortium. Partners use this platform for initialization and parametrization of models, running and stopping simulations. The integrated platform couples the simulation tools and models developed in WP2-WP5 in series and includes a data exchange between models.

Deliverable Review

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 6.1 documents the Serial Integrated Simulation Platform that we developed in Task 6.1, and which we delivered to the partners of the Upwards consortium. The objective of Task 6.1 was to define and provide to partners a software platform, which integrates all software systems used to perform physical simulations on wind parks and turbines. This platform couples and executes these simulation systems in a serial workflow and finally provides an overall insight of high fidelity simulation results related to the atmospheric states at a wind park location, the flow fields within a wind park, the states of each turbine and blades, and the noise fields generated by turbines.

The platform allows users:

1. To setup wind turbine and park simulations with initial conditions and model parameters.
2. To execute wind turbine and park simulation systems within a workflow step.
3. To pass results from one simulation system as input to another simulation system.
4. To visualize generated simulation results.

The aim of Task 6.1 was to build an open access interface (see Figure 1). It links all the software simulation tools developed in UPWARDS in one integrated framework. These open access interfaces will be designed meeting two requirements:

1. It will be possible to replace each tool by third party products when considering the application interfaces, and
2. They will have the capability to be linked with additional tools.

To that end, and not to interfere with the partners' IPR, the source code of each partner will not be open access, but an application interface to initialize and run the simulation is provided, with guidelines on how to use it and which will be open.

Figure 1: Open Interface Simulation Framework

Figure 2 gives an overview about the concept and design of Upwards. As pointed out by the orange rectangle, this deliverable focuses on the model layer and implements a serial version of the workflow.

Figure 2: Conceptual design of Upwards simulation framework

1.1. Contributions to project objectives

The concept underpinning UPWARDS is to develop an integrated simulation framework of high fidelity simulation codes capable of performing high fidelity wind turbine and wind energy park simulations including wind flow, fully coupled fluid structure interaction, progressive damage and noise propagation

The implementation of this platform contributes to the project objectives of the Upwards agreement:

Objective 1:

Establish a high fidelity multi-physics, mechatronic and multi-scale simulation framework for wind turbines that enables integrated modelling of wind flow, mechanical movements, structural/control dynamics, and stresses with a level of details that today only is achievable in modelling of isolated phenomena.

- b) State of the simulation tools and models for wind flow from atmospheric to turbine scale, rotor noise generation and propagation and composite material damage models. Methods and protocols will be developed to link these tools to enable efficient sequential modelling of all scales and physics.

Objective 3:

Generate in-depth knowledge of important wind turbine related physical phenomena through high fidelity simulations.

- a) High fidelity simulations of important wind turbine related phenomena will be performed using the high-fidelity simulation framework described in Objective 1 to exploit and increase the understanding of their physical behaviour and interaction.

Objective 5:

Distribute and enable further use of the generated knowledge, data, and results

- e) HPC Simulation Interface linking different type of simulation tools and models

1.2. Document outline

This documentation provides explanation to all components used to implement the Serial Integrated Simulation Platform:

Section 2

- The workflow to combine physical simulation systems
- The models and parameters that are involved in this workflow
- The systems that use these models to simulate physical behaviours

Section 3

- The technical foundations to encapsulate systems in software containers
- The application interface to initialize and run the simulation
- The data exchange interfaces in between systems

Section 4

- A guiding example that shows the overall simulation setup of a virtual wind park located in Østerild, Denmark.

Partners of the Upwards consortium access the platform by using the Gitlab collaboration platform hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM (<https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards>).

Figure 3: Upward's wind park simulation workflow

2. The Upwards Workflow in between physical simulation models

Figure 3 summarizes the workflow of Upwards high fidelity wind park simulation. The workflow consists of four workflow steps:

1. Starting from the geo location of a planned wind park, the **atmospheric model** simulates spatial and temporal wind conditions (velocity, direction, pressure) on atmospheric scale. The partner AWS provides a tailored version of the Open Source LES-simulation system WRF^4 (Weather Research and Forecast Model).
2. Based on these wind conditions, and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the **park model** simulates wind conditions on park and neighborhood scale in between the wind turbines in terms of turbulent flow fields (velocity vectors, pressure). For this workflow step, the partner SINTEF provides solvers and models⁵ specialized on wind parks that can be executed by the Open Source simulation system $OpenFoam^6$.
3. Based on the inflow conditions around each turbine, the **fluid-structure (Aeroelastic) interaction analysis** simulates the wind forces attacking the structural components (e.g., blades, shaft, and tower) of the turbine. The forces accumulate to progressive composite structure damage models. The partners SAMTECH, UNL, SISW, AaU, SINTEF, and SWP provide a coupled software stack consisting of commercial systems $STAR-CCM+$ (Wind 3D CFD model) and $SAMCEF$ (Wind Turbine 3D non-linear Finite Element Analysis model, including kinematics and control), to achieve these simulations.
4. Based on the global and local inflow conditions of the park and around each turbine the partners IVKDF and SISW simulate a **noise propagation** in terms of noise levels by Empirical models for noise production coupled with ray-tracing atmospheric propagation model. They provide a software stack, which also incorporates among other software tools $STAR-CCM+$ to reach this goal.

⁴ <https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/weather-research-and-forecasting-model>

⁵ Extensions of models provided by NREL/SOWFA <https://github.com/NREL/SOWFA>

⁶ <https://www.openfoam.com/>

To summarize, the serial integrated simulation system executes a workflow, which connects four models (i.e., atmospheric, park, fluid structure interaction, and noise) with respective software systems.

3. Technical foundations of the serial integration framework

The following aspects summarize the implementation of the serial integrated simulation system:

- At Fraunhofer ITWM, all models and software tools run on a virtual machine (16 CPUs, 16.384 GB memory, 576 GB storage) with a Linux based operating system (RHEL 4.8.5).
- All models and software tools that are part of a workflow step are encapsulated within an individual software container (Docker 1.13.1), respectively.
- The Partners in Upwards created a convention to standardize the program interface of each software tool / container, which defines a bash script named `runAll.sh` that handles program initialization and execution.
- The `runAll.sh` script takes model parameters and initial conditions from a text file in JSON format, called `input_params.json`.
- The respective container should serialize evaluation results to files, which can be interpreted by the Runtime environment of the serial integrated simulation platform, which is implemented in Python 3.

Figure 4 shows the use of software containers to implement and to execute the workflow steps shown in Figure 3 by means of Docker. We decided to use the implementation of Docker as basis for containerization, as it is the most popular container format, yet. It also provides capabilities for parallelized HPC, which will be scope in later work packages WP 6.3 and WP 6.4. As one contribution of Upwards is to provide the integration system with all components as Open Accessible Framework, we specified a concrete format that each container has to follow to be used in Upwards, which means to be integrated within the workflow.

Figure 4: Upward's containerized wind park simulation workflow

3.1. Containerization via Docker

"A container is a standard unit of software that packages up code and all its dependencies so the application runs quickly and reliably from one computing environment to another. A Docker container

image is a lightweight, standalone, executable package of software that includes everything needed to run an application: code, runtime, system tools, system libraries and settings. Container images become containers at runtime and in the case of Docker containers - images become containers when they run on Docker Engine. Available for both Linux and Windows-based applications, containerized software will always run the same, regardless of the infrastructure. Containers isolate software from its environment and ensure that it works uniformly despite differences for instance between development and staging. (<https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>)”

Each software applications in Upwards, such as WRF, OPENFOAM, STAR-CCM+, SAMSEF is encapsulated as Docker container, which finally transforms the software application to a standalone micro service, which partners can easily package and deliver as container images. This facilitates the update of new versions for integrating latest results from WP2-WP5. A so-called Dockerfile defines the content of an executable container image. Figure 5 shows an example Dockerfile that encapsulates the open source CFD toolbox OPENFOAM.


```

1 # Start from the official Ubuntu Bionic (18.04 LTS) image
2 FROM ubuntu:bionic
3
4 # Install any extra things we might need
5 RUN apt-get update \
6     && apt-get install -y \
7         vim \
8         ssh \
9         make \
10        sudo \
11        wget \
12        software-properties-common ;\
13        rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/*
14
15 # Create a new user called foam
16 RUN useradd --user-group --create-home --shell /bin/bash foam ;\
17     echo "foam ALL=(ALL) NOPASSWD:ALL" >> /etc/sudoers
18
19 # Install OpenFOAM v6 (without ParaView)
20 # including configuring for use by user=foam
21 # plus an extra environment variable to make OpenMPI play nice
22 RUN sh -c "wget -O - http://dl.openfoam.org/gpg.key | apt-key add -" ;\
23     add-apt-repository http://dl.openfoam.org/ubuntu ;\
24     apt-get update ;\
25     apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends openfoam6 ;\
26     rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/* ;\
27     echo "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc" >> ~foam/.bashrc ;\
28     echo "export OMPI_MCA_btl_vader_single_copy_mechanism=none" >> ~foam/.bashrc
29
30 # Copy binaries of OffwindModel and OffwindSolver
31 ADD linux64GccDPInt320pt /opt/openfoam6/platforms/linux64GccDPInt320pt
32
33 #ADD applications /opt/openfoam6/applications
34 #ADD applications/solvers/windenergy/OffwindSolver/OffwindModels /opt/openfoam6/src/OffwindModels
35 #RUN /bin/bash -c "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc ;\
36 # cd /opt/openfoam6/src/OffwindModels ;\
37 # wmake libso"
38 #RUN /bin/bash -c "source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc ;\
39 # cd /opt/openfoam6/applications/solvers/windenergy/OffwindSolver ;\
40 # wmake libso"
41
42 # set the default container user to foam
43 USER foam

```

Figure 5: Example Dockerfile of the container that encapsulates OPENFOAM

If possible, build routines used inside the Dockerfile should request open source binaries and public available data from Web resources. Closed source binaries and data are provided in Gitlab, which is only accessible by partners of the Upwards consortium agreement. This enables partners to access and build containers with closed source proprietary software systems such as STAR-CCM+

or SAMCEF. Required license files and network addresses of respective license servers have to be configurable within the `Dockerfile`.

3.2. Program interface

The serial integrated simulation platform runs applications as Docker containers. We standardized the program interface such that each container is executed by running a shell command called `runAll.sh`. Figure 6 shows the `runAll.sh` script that executes a simulation of the OPENFOAM container. This script takes input data from files and writes simulation results into files. These file are stored at the host system and mounted into the container runtime.


```

1 # Source OpenFOAM BASH profile
2 source /opt/openfoam6/etc/bashrc
3
4 # Export fix for OPENMPI in a container
5 export OMPI_MCA_btl_vader_single_copy_mechanism=none
6
7 # Run OpenFoam command batch
8 blockMesh
9 snappyHexMesh -overwrite
10 decomposePar
11 . $WM_PROJECT_DIR/bin/tools/RunFunctions
12 runParallel OffwindSolver
13 reconstructPar

```

Figure 6: Example program interface of the OPENFOAM container

The execution of a Docker container is triggered by using the Docker API. Inside the Linux machine, it is possible to call the Docker API by using a shell command called `Docker` or by using the Python software framework `py_upwards` (see Section 3.5). The example presented in Figure 7 shows a command line call based execution of the OPENFOAM container.

<code>docker container run</code>	<i>Request the docker API by using the command shell program "docker".</i>
<code>--rm</code>	<i>Close container runtime after execution.</i>
<code>-v \$PWD/projects/transient:/home/foam/data:z</code>	<i>Mount a folder from host system within the containerized runtime</i>
<code>-w /home/foam/data</code>	<i>Set the working directory within the container runtime</i>
<code>myopenfoam:v6.0</code>	<i>Name of the container</i>
<code>/bin/bash -c "./runAll.sh"</code>	<i>Command to execute within the container runtime. By convention all containers of the integrated platform call this script runAll.sh</i>

Figure 7: Executing the OPENFOAM container

Finally, we summarize the software conventions of Upwards as follows:

1. Software containers represent each workflow step.
2. The `Dockerfile` describes the content and structure of a software container.
3. The `runAll.sh` script executes a software container.

This allows users to exchange each software system by other implementations, in principle.

3.3. Simulation models and systems

The partners of the Upwards consortium delivered their software systems of the workflow steps in form of software containers. This resembles the objective of milestone MS11 (Interface Description/communication protocol), reached at September 2019. They containerized all necessary software systems being involved within a workflow step.

We manage container images and respective build scripts (`Dockerfile`) in the collaboration platform Gitlab (see Data Management Plan in D.1.4 for more information). We provide each work package with an individual development branch. Figure 8 lists the these development branches:

Workflow step	Encapsulated software	Repository location
atmospheric model (WP2)	WRF	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP2/WP2%2Fwrf_docker
park model (WP2)	OPENFOAM	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP6/WP6%2Fcontainer%2Fdocker
fluid-structure interaction analysis (WP3,5)	STAR-CCM+, SAMSEF	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP3/WP3%2Fcontainer%2Fdocker
noise propagation (WP4)	STAR-CCM+	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP4/WP4%2Fcontainer%2Fdocker%2Fexample_starccm_process

Figure 8: Overview of containers in Upwards

3.4. Data exchange interface

The data exchange interface defines the data format of initial conditions, model parameters, and simulation results. A convention in Upwards is that all input parameters are serialized in JSON notation in a file called `input_params.json`.

Atmospheric model

The atmospheric model calculates the wind conditions in atmosphere scale within the area of the wind park. Therefore, it requires initial conditions about:

- the latitude and longitude coordinates of the geo position of the park,
- the dimension (length, width, height) of the park,
- the date in time (day, month, year).

In order to serialize an inlet layer for the park model, it is necessary to specify layers in height. Figure shows an example content of the file `input_params.json` in JSON notation:

```

{
  'grid_size': {
    'x': 2000,
    'y': 800,
    'z': 244
  },
  'lat': 57.0492938,
  'long': 8.886445,
  'month': 2,
  'year': 2020,
  'day': 29,
  'inlet_z_layers_velocity': { 8: [ (0, 0, 244),
                                     (0, 0, 210),
                                     (0, 0, 178),
                                     (0, 0, 140),
                                     (0, 0, 106),
                                     (0, 0, 70),
                                     (0, 0, 40),
                                     (0, 0, 10)]},
}

```

Figure 9: Input parameter of atmospheric model in JSON notation

Park model

The park model calculates the wind conditions in park and neighborhood scale within the area of the wind park. It requires initial conditions about:

- park dimensions
- initial distribution of wind velocity and pressure, settings of k-epsilon turbulence parameters
- turbine types (e.g., NREL 5 MW, Siemens SWT 2.3, Upwards 15 MW)
- turbine positions and geometries (e.g., tower height, hub radius, tip radius, yaw angle, tilt angle)
- rotor states (e.g., rotation speed, pitch angle)
- Mesh configuration (lower resolution block mesh, high resolution hex mesh)
- Simulation times (start, end, delta_t, write interval)

Figure 10 shows an example content of the file `input_params.json` in JSON notation. The framework of `OPENFOAM` allows plenty of more parameters to configure. We used the Python library `PyFoam` (<https://pypi.org/project/PyFoam/>) in our integration framework `py_upwards` to parse the complete configuration of `OPENFOAM` projects. This enabled us to list only those parameters that differ from default values into the `input_params.json`.

```

{
  'block_mesh_dimension': [
    [-200, 126.2, 0],
    [-200, 126.2, 400.0],
    [-200, -126.2, 400.0],
    [-200, -126.2, 0],
    [757.2, 126.2, 0],
    [757.2, 126.2, 400.0],
    [757.2, -126.2, 400.0],
    [757.2, -126.2, 0]],
  'delta_t': 0.02,
  'endTime': 100,
  'hex_mesh_dimensions': {
    'turbine1': {
      'point1': [-5, 0, 200.0],
      'point2': [5, 0, 200.0],
      'radius': 100,
      'type': 'searchableCylinder'}}},
  'inletFlowVelocity': [(8, 0, 0)],
  'startTime': 0,
  'turbineArray': {
    'globalProperties': {
      'outputControl': '"timeStep"',
      'outputInterval': 1},
    'turbine1': {
      'Azimuth': 280.3935,
      'NacYaw': 270,
      'Pitch': 0,
      'RotSpeed': 10.9874,
      'baseLocation': [0, 0, 0],
      'bladeUpdateType': '"oldPosition"',
      'epsilon': 3.5,
      'fluidDensity': 1.25,
      'numBladePoints': 40,
      'pointDistType': '"uniform"',
      'pointInterpType': '"linear"',
      'rotationDir': '"cw"',
      'tipRootLossCorrType': '"none"',
      'turbineType': '"NREL5MWRef"'}}}},
  'turbine_locations': [(0, 0, 0)],
  'turbulentEpsilon': 0.55296,
  'turbulentKE': 0.96,
  'write_interval': 1000
}

```

Figure 10: Input parameter of park model in JSON notation

Wind Structure Interaction

The wind-structure interaction model calculates forces that are induced by wind conditions within the park to each structural component of contained wind turbine. It requires initial conditions about:

- Flow fields in wind park from park simulation in scale of turbine neighborhoods
- turbine types (e.g., NREL 5 MW, Siemens SWT 2.3, Upwards 15 MW)
- turbine positions and geometries (e.g., tower height, hub radius, tip radius, yaw angle, tilt angle)
- rotor states (e.g., rotation speed, pitch angle)
- Simulation times (start, end, delta_t, write interval)

Figure 13 shows an example content of the file `input_params.json` in JSON notation.

```

{
  'WT1': {
    'position': [0, 0, 0],
    'rpm': 10.9874,
    'turbineType': '"NRELSMWRef"',
    'yaw': 270},
  'turbine_flow_fields': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/case_8/park_sim_8/postprocessing/surfaces'
}

```

Figure 11: Input parameter of wind-structure interaction model in JSON notation

Noise model

The noise model calculates the noise production within the area of the wind park. It requires initial conditions about each wind turbine:

- turbines location
- mean flow fields in wind park from park simulation
- turbine types (e.g., NREL 5 MW, Siemens SWT 2.3, Upwards 15 MW)
- turbine positions and geometries (e.g., tower height, hub radius, tip radius, yaw angle, tilt angle)
- rotor states (e.g., rotation speed, pitch angle)
- simulation times (start, end, delta_t, write interval)

Figure 11 shows an example content of the file `input_params.json` in JSON notation. In Section 3.5, we will show how to pass parameters from park model here.

```

{
  'WT1': {
    'position': [0, 0, 0],
    'rpm': 10.9874,
    'turbineType': '"NRELSMWRef"',
    'yaw': 270},
  'turbine_flow_fields': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/case_8/park_sim_8'
}

```

Figure 12: Input parameter of noise model in JSON notation

Figure 12 shows flow fields resulting from the park simulation. The noise simulation takes these values as input. Here, these results represent mean pressure distributions in the wind park.

```

/*-----*- C++ -*-----*\
=====
\\      /   F i e l d           |   OpenFOAM: The Open Source CFD Toolbox
\\    /    O p e r a t i o n    |   Website: https://openfoam.org
\\  /     A n d                 |   Version: 6
\\ /      M a n i p u l a t i o n |
\*-----*\

FoamFile
{
  version      2.0;
  format       ascii;
  class        volScalarField;
  location     "100";
  object       pMean;
}
// *****

dimensions     [0 2 -2 0 0 0 0];

internalField  nonuniform List<scalar>
280852
(
2.58225
2.88852
2.86111
2.86228
2.87968
2.90233
2.92257
2.9388
2.95621
2.97472
2.99415
3.01418
3.0346
3.05516
3.07551
3.09564
3.11552
3.13453
3.15254
3.16962
3.18541

```

Figure 13: 3D mean pressure values

Summary

Finally, the most important input conditions and model parameters in the wind park simulation are:

- The flow fields (pressure and velocity)
- The virtual park dimension (location, length, height, width)
- The turbine positions and geometries (e.g., turbine type, tower height, hub radius, tip radius, yaw angle, tilt angle)
- rotor states (e.g., rotation speed, pitch angle)
- Simulation times (start, end, delta_t, write interval)

Flow fields are passed from park model to the structure interaction model and noise model by non-standardized output files, which are parsed and transformed differently, depending on the software system. Model parameters are passed from model to model in JSON⁷ notation by using the canonical file `input_params.json`. In tasks 6.3, 6.4, 6.7, and 7.3, we expect an increasing count of parameters as the complexity of used models increase from results of WP2-5.

⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON>

3.5. Py upwards

We developed the software framework `py_upwards` to provide a base for configuring models, running the workflow, starting workflow steps by means of containers, collect result data and visualize or persist these. It consists of following components:

- We created a runtime environment for simulations in style of a **workbench** and used the iPython Jupyter Notebook⁸ as base for implementation, here.
- We developed a Python **software library** called `py_upwards`⁹ with functions to parse, represent, convert, analyze and visualize data. The library is available within the **simulation workbench**.

Figure 14 shows the workbench within a Jupyter Notebook in a Browser window. The notebook allows the users to integrate and run Python code, start containers, load images, and draw figures. In combination with `py_upwards`, it provides a flexible development environment for evaluating wind park simulations in Upwards.

Simulation workbench

We decided to use Jupyter Notebooks as base platform for performing simulation runs in Upwards integrated simulation system.

Figure 14: Simulation workbench within a Jupyter Notebook

The Jupyter Notebook is an open-source web application that allows you to create and share documents that contain live code, equations, visualizations and narrative text. Uses include: data

⁸ <https://jupyter.org/>

⁹ https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/master/py_upwards

cleaning and transformation, numerical simulation, statistical modeling, data visualization, machine learning, and much more. (<https://jupyter.org/>)

It provides us with the flexibility to perform a loose coupling of workflow steps. This facilitates the integration of the evolving models and systems, which the Upwards partners are developing. Another advantage of the notebook format is that it contains results of simulation runs. Users can view these results in Web browsers, even without running an iPython kernel underneath. In Upwards, we use this feature to preserve simulation results to the Gitlab collaboration platform. This way of managing data analysis results is popular and also used by scientific communities like <https://www.kaggle.com/> or <https://github.com/>.

Software library

The software library we developed in WP 6.1 provides a set of features, which facilitate the setup and analysis of simulation runs in the simulation workbench. Partners can find it in Gitlab at https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/master/py_upwards.

`Py_upwards` extends and depends on existing open source frameworks of the Python ecosystem. For data representation, we used matrix implementations from `NumPy`¹⁰ and data frame representations from `pandas`¹¹. Visualization of standard charts and figures is performed by using `Matplotlib`¹². 3D visualizations and rendering of CAD is implemented based on `K3D`¹³ and `VTK`¹⁴. `SciPy` performs the analysis of snapshots data¹⁵. Modal analysis, system analysis and model order reductions are implemented by using `PyDMD`¹⁶. The handling of `OpenFoam` projects has been implemented by using `PyFoam`¹⁷. The management of Docker containers is done by `docker-py`¹⁸.

Example features of the `py_upwards` library are:

- Parse, modify and create configuration files for workflow steps.
- Parse, transform and pass simulation results in between workflow steps
 - Extracts 2d-surfaces from 3d-flow fields for being used as inlet data of succeeding sub-simulations (here, noise and wind-structure-interaction)
- Automatic creation of wind park simulations that can be executed by `OpenFoam`
 - Facilitate creation of steady state and transient simulations
 - Automates block mesh definition based on turbine placement
 - Automates calculation of turbulence parameter based on initial wind speed.
- Execute workflow steps by initializing and starting Docker containers.

¹⁰ <https://numpy.org/>

¹¹ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

¹² <https://matplotlib.org/>

¹³ <https://pypi.org/project/K3D/>

¹⁴ <https://pypi.org/project/vtk/>

¹⁵ <https://www.scipy.org/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/mathLab/PyDMD>

¹⁷ <https://pypi.org/project/PyFoam/>

¹⁸ <https://docker-py.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

4. End-to-End example

Here, we will describe the developed demonstrator by following the use case of simulating a single wind turbine located in the Denmark area of the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field¹⁹. Systematically, we show how the integrated simulation platform helps to investigate the different aspects of atmospheric conditions, wind park conditions, noise fields and fluid-structure interactions.

The presented results of this example use case can be download from GitLab by Upwards partners at <https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/blob/master/platform/>

4.1. *Initializing the simulation case*

At first, we have to initialize the simulation case, which means we define the workflow steps to execute. For each step, we assign the implementing Docker container and the respective project folder name. Figure 15 shows how to implement it within the simulation workbench by using the library `py_upwards`:

Initialize integrated simulation platform

setup program interface

```
client = docker.from_env()

workflow_steps = [ "atmosphere" , "park", "fluid_structure", "noise"]

# Folder that contains simulation projects
path = "./case_8"

# Container registry that maps workflow steps to Docker containers.
container_registry = {
    workflow_steps[0] : "wrf:latest",
    workflow_steps[1] : "myopenfoam:v6.1",
    workflow_steps[2] : "mecano-star:latest",
    workflow_steps[3] : "example_starccm_process:latest"
}

# Simulation registry that maps workflow steps to simulation projects.
simulation_registry = {
    workflow_steps[0] : "atmospheric_sim_osterild",
    workflow_steps[1] : "park_sim_8",
    workflow_steps[2] : "fluid_structure_cosim",
    workflow_steps[3] : "noise_sim"
}
```

Figure 15: Initializing a simulation case

Figure 16 shows a log entry, `py_upwards` serialized after initializing the simulation case. It can be seen, that three registries (container registry, simulation registry, and workspace registry) carry information about the involved workflow steps and data management. The program interfaces of all workflow steps are initialized with access rights, such that containers may execute these.

¹⁹ <https://www.vindenergi.dtu.dk/english/test-centers/oesterild>

```

Container Registry
{
  'atmosphere': 'wrf:latest',
  'fluid_structure': 'mecano-star:latest',
  'noise': 'example_starccm_process:latest',
  'park': 'myopenfoam:v6.1'}

Simulation Registry
{
  'atmosphere': 'atmospheric_sim_osterild',
  'fluid_structure': 'fluid_structure_cosim',
  'noise': 'noise_sim',
  'park': 'park_sim_8'}

Workspace Registry
{
  'atmosphere': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/atmospheric_sim_osterild',
  'fluid_structure': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/fluid_structure_cosim',
  'noise': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/noise_sim',
  'park': '/opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/park_sim_8'}

Bootstrap program interface
set access rights 777 to step atmosphere in program interface:
  /opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/atmospheric_sim_osterild/runAll.sh

set access rights 777 to step park in program interface:
  /opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/park_sim_8/runAll.sh

set access rights 777 to step fluid_structure in program interface:
  /opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/fluid_structure_cosim/runAll.sh

set access rights 777 to step noise in program interface:
  /opt/data/WP6/WP6/DMD/py_upwards/doc/./case_8/noise_sim/runAll.sh

```

Figure 16: Initialized data structures of a simulation case

Next, the data binding has to be configured, which enables workflow steps (here `noise` and `fluid_structure`) to use flow field results from the park model. Figure 17 shows how to setup the data binding in the simulation workbench.

Setup data interface

```

data_binding = {
  workflow_steps[0] : { #atmosphere
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[0]]+ '/data'      : {'bind': '/home/wrf/data', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[0]]+ '/options'   : {'bind': '/home/wrf/options', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[0]]+ '/scripts'   : {'bind': '/home/wrf/scripts', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[0]]+ '/.cdsapirc' : {'bind': '/home/wrf/.cdsapirc', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[0]]+ '/runAll.sh' : {'bind': '/home/wrf/runAll.sh', 'mode': 'Z'}
  },
  workflow_steps[1] : { #park
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[1]]              : {'bind': '/home/foam/data', 'mode': 'Z'}
  },
  workflow_steps[2] : { #fluid-structure
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[2]]              : {'bind': '/home/mecano-star', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[1]]+ '/postprocessing/surfaces':
      {'bind': '/home/mecano-star/turbine_flow_fields', 'mode': 'Z'}
  },
  workflow_steps[3] : { #noise
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[3]]+ '/data'     : {'bind': '/home/noise/data', 'mode': 'Z'},
    workspace_registry[workflow_steps[1]]              : {'bind': '/home/noise/park_mean_flow_fields', 'mode': 'Z'}
  },
}

```

Figure 17: Defining the data binding in between workflow steps

4.2. Locating the wind park

Second, we locate the wind turbines to the area of the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field. This can be done by filling the input parameters of the atmospheric model. In addition, the model expects more details about the date, the grid size and the number of height layers. Figure 18 shows the setting for simulating atmospheric flow fields in the area of the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field. As it can be seen, it is possible to add further descriptions and notes to the simulation case in the simulation workbench.

Park Location

Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

Some of the 7 turbines. The distance between them is about 600 meters. Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field (alternatively Risø) is a facility managed by the DTU Risø Campus of the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) for testing of offshore wind turbines with a pinnacle height up to 330 metres (1,080 ft) near Thisted-Østerild, Denmark.

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Atmospheric Model

```

atmosphere_input_params = {
  "lat" : 57.0492938,
  "long" : 8.886445,
  "year" : 2020,
  "month" : 2,
  "day" : 29,
  "grid_size" : {
    "x" : 2000,
    "y" : 800,
    "z" : 244
  },
  "inlet_z_layers_velocity" : { 8:
    [(0, 0, 244),
     (0, 0, 210),
     (0, 0, 178),
     (0, 0, 140),
     (0, 0, 106),
     (0, 0, 70),
     (0, 0, 40),
     (0, 0, 10)]
  }
}
store_input_parameters(atmosphere_input_params, step=workflow_steps[0] )

```

Figure 18: Input parameters for simulating atmospheric flow fields of the Østerild Test Field

By using `py_upwards` it is possible to render the location on a map by using the Google maps API. Figure 19 shows the location of the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field.

Figure 19: Map visualization of the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

4.3. Simulating flow fields in atmospheric scales

Next, we trigger the execution of the atmospheric simulation of this workflow step by executing the container's program interface. Figure 20 shows the standardized program interface that invokes the execution of the WRF container.

```
client.containers.run(
    container_registry[workflow_steps[0]],
    "bash runAll.sh",
    auto_remove=True,
    volumes = data_binding[workflow_steps[0]],
    working_dir="/home/wrf")
```

Figure 20: Program interface that invokes the execution of the WRF container

Results of the atmospheric analysis (here, wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric pressure, and temperature) within the area of the wind park are shown in Figures 21-24. Each charts displays the results for the specified date, which is February, the 29th 2020.

wind speed profile

```
visualize_atm_wind_speed(atmosphere_initial_conditions["year"], atmosphere_initial_conditions["month"],atmosphere_initial_conditi
```


Figure 21: Wind speed gradient in the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

Wind direction profile

```
visualize_atm_wind_direction(atmosphere_initial_conditions["year"], atmosphere_initial_conditions["month"],atmosphere_initial_cor
```


Figure 22: Wind direction gradient in the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

Pressure profile

```
visualize_atm_pressure(atmosphere_initial_conditions["year"], atmosphere_initial_conditions["month"],atmosphere_initial_conditior
```


Figure 23: Atmospheric pressure gradient in the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

```
IFrame("http://rodeo.dtu.dk/rodeo/GraphicsStreamer.aspx?&Project=179&Year={}&Month={}&Day={}&Interval=OneDay&GraphIndex=4&PageNam
```


Figure 24: Temperature gradient in the Østerild Wind Turbine Test Field

4.4. Defining the wind park

After having calculated typical wind profiles for the given park location, we can start defining the wind park. We place wind turbines of specific type at locations within the park. Figure 25 shows the input parameters of our test wind park, with a single wind turbine at location $[0, 0, 0]$. From the wind profile, we select an inlet wind velocity of 8 m/s and let the wind flow in a vertical direction to the turbine's rotor.

Define park

```
park_input_params = {
  "block_mesh_dimension" : sim.blockMesh["vertices"],
  "hex_mesh_dimensions" : sim.snappyHexMesh.content["geometry"],
  "turbineArray" : sim.turbineArray.content,
  "turbine_locations" : [(0, 0, 0)],
  "inletFlowVelocity" : [(8, 0, 0)],
  "startTime" : 0, # in s
  "endTime" : 100, # in s
  "delta_t" : 0.02, # length of step
  "write_interval" : 1000, # steps
}
store_input_parameters(park_input_params, workspace_registry[workflow_steps[1]] )
```

Figure 25: Input parameters of the test wind park

Next, we setup a steady state simulation case, which simulates 100 seconds and serializes snapshots of the simulated flow fields in park scale every 2 seconds. Figure 26 shows the grid visualization of the park simulation. Blue rectangles represent areas of block meshes. The oval area surrounding the red turbine rotor represents the area of a hex mesh of high resolution.

```
sim.setup_steady_state_simulation(
    initial_u=park_input_params['inletFlowVelocity'][0][0],
    start_time=park_input_params['startTime'],
    end_time = park_input_params['endTime'],
    delta_t=park_input_params['delta_t'],
    write_interval=park_input_params['write_interval'],
    park=park_input_params['turbine_locations'])
```

Visualize park with grid areas.

- Blue areas contain block mesh
- Red ovals contain fine granular hex mesh

```
sim.plot_park()
```


Figure 26: Grid visualization of the park simulation

The library `py_upwards` allows to set more parameters such as the turbine type, mesh resolutions, etc. However, it would exceed the scale of this documentation to list all of these.

4.5. Flow field simulations in wind park scale

Now, it is possible to invoke the container of the wind park simulation. Figure 27 shows the standardized program interface that invokes the execution of the `OPENFOAM` container. The invocation also includes a post-processing step, which extracts mean flow fields and surfaces nearby each turbine. This information is required by fluid-structure interaction and noise model. Please refer to Figure 17: Defining the data binding in between workflow steps. There, you see how the containers of fluid-structure interaction and noise can access these results.

Execute Park Model

```
client.containers.run(
    container_registry[workflow_steps[1]],
    "bash runAll.sh",
    auto_remove=True,
    volumes = data_binding[workflow_steps[1]],
    working_dir="/home/foam/data")
```

```
client.containers.run(
    container_registry[workflow_steps[1]],
    "bash runPost.sh",
    auto_remove=True,
    volumes = data_binding[workflow_steps[1]],
    working_dir="/home/foam/data")
```

Figure 27: Program interface that invokes the execution of the OPENFOAM container

The library `py_upwards`, facilitates parsing simulated flow-field snapshots. It represents loaded data (here, wind velocities and pressure distributions) in efficient `Numpy` arrays. In Figure 28, we parse results of the park simulation so that we have access to it within the simulation workbench.

load flow field snapshot data

```
grid = load.openfoam_grid(sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv", load = True, skew = True)
```

```
data_dict_U = load.load_Data("U", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_p = load.load_Data("p", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
```

convert data to Pandas, a Python library which is supported my popular visualisation and machine learning frameworks

```
sim.velocities = pd.DataFrame(np.array(data_dict_U["data"]).T)
sim.pressure = pd.DataFrame(np.array(data_dict_p["data"]).T)
```

Figure 28: Parsing wind park simulation results

After having access to flow fields by using `Numpy` arrays, `py_upwards` provides convenience methods to visualize flow fields in regions of interest. Figure 29 shows two slicing surfaces, which are located 10m behind the wind turbine. The upper chart plots the L2 norm of a 2D pressure distribution. The lower chart shows the L2 norm of a 2D wind velocity distribution.

plot 2d surface flow fields

```
turbine_inlet = support.extract_inlet(grid, [0,0,200], width_z = 70, width_y = 70, dist_x = 10, alpha = 270, beta = 0)
```

```
plot.plot_inlet(data_dict_p, turbine_inlet, 'norm', 4, [-200, 757.2], [-126.2, 126.2], [0,400])
```



```
plot.plot_inlet(data_dict_U, turbine_inlet, 'norm', 4, [-200, 757.2], [-126.2, 126.2], [0,400])
```


Figure 29: Visualize flow fields in regions of interest

4.6. Simulating wind-structure interactions

Now, after having calculated flow fields within the wind park, we can investigate in the interaction in between flow fields in wind parks and structures of wind turbines. The respective model requires input settings describing detailed information about each wind turbine. It can infer shape and dimensions of turbines by using the type reference. Figure 30 shows the input parameters of our test wind park, with a single wind turbine WT1.

Wind Structure Interaction

Models

```
fluid_structure_input_params = {
  "WT1":
  {
    "turbineType": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["turbineType"],
    "position": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["baseLocation"],
    "yaw": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["NacYaw"],
    "rpm": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["RotSpeed"]
  }
}

store_input_parameters(fluid_structure_input_params, workspace_registry[workflow_steps[2]] )
```

Figure 30: Input parameters of the fluid-structure co-simulation

Figure 31 shows the standardized program interface that invokes the execution of the co-simulating container. The data binding contains references to the relevant flow field slices from the park model that surround the wind turbine.

```

client.containers.run(
    container_registry[workflow_steps[2]],
    "bash runAll.sh",
    auto_remove=True,
    volumes = data_binding[workflow_steps[2]],
    working_dir="/home/mecano-star"
)

```

Figure 31: Program interface that invokes the co-simulating container

After having simulated the effects of wind on blades, rotor, and tower, we use `py_upwards` to parse time series on wind turbine states and represent these in efficient `Pandas` data frames. Figure 32 shows how to use respective convenience methods for performing this task.

Load simulated turbine states

```

data_dict_rotSpeed = load.load_Data("rotSpeed", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_powerRotor = load.load_Data("powerRotor", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_thrust = load.load_Data("thrust", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_torqueGen = load.load_Data("torqueGen", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_torqueRotor = load.load_Data("torqueRotor", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_azimuth = load.load_Data("azimuth", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_nacYaw = load.load_Data("nacYaw", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
data_dict_pitch = load.load_Data("pitch", sim.path + "/" + sim.name+ "_csv")
sim.rotSpeed = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_rotSpeed, columns = ["rotSpeed"])
sim.powerRotor = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_powerRotor, columns = ["powerRotor"])
sim.thrust = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_thrust, columns = ["thrust"])
sim.torqueGen = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_torqueGen, columns = ["torqueGen"])
sim.torqueRotor = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_torqueRotor, columns = ["torqueRotor"])
sim.azimuth = pd.DataFrame(data_dict_azimuth, columns = ["azimuth"])

```

Figure 32: Parsing time series on wind turbine states

Again, the internal representation of simulation results enables us to visualize these. Starting with the rotation speed, the gradient in Figure 33 shows how the turbine rotor enters a steady state with nine rotations per second after 3000 time steps (~ 60s). The visualization of azimuth, yaw, and pitch angles require a transformation from degrees to radians. The chart representation of azimuth states shows a sine like oscillation with a small chirp, emerging from the transient phase. Pitch and yaw angles remain stable, as wind speed and direction does not change. Similar to the rotation speed, the power distribution curves reach a steady state after 3000 time steps (~ 60s).

Visualize turbine states

```
fig, axes = plt.subplots(nrows=1, ncols=3, figsize=(20,5))

my_data_frame = pd.DataFrame(index=range(5000))
my_data_frame["rotSpeed"] = sim.rotSpeed[0:5000]
my_data_frame.plot(title="Rotation speed", ax=axes[0])

angles = pd.DataFrame(index=range(5000))
angles["azimuth"] = np.sin((sim.azimuth[0:5000]/360)*2*np.pi)
angles["nacYaw"] = np.sin(pd.DataFrame(data_dict_nacYaw, columns = ["nacYaw"])[0:5000]/360*2*np.pi)
angles["pitch"] = np.sin(pd.DataFrame(data_dict_pitch, columns = ["pitch"])[0:5000]/360*2*np.pi)

angles.plot(ax=axes[1], title="Azimuth, nacYaw, and pitch angle of rotor and blades")

rotor = pd.DataFrame(index=range(5000))
rotor["torqueRotor"] = sim.torqueRotor[0:5000]
rotor["powerRotor"] = sim.powerRotor[0:5000]
rotor["thrust"] = sim.thrust[0:5000]
rotor["torqueGen"] = sim.torqueGen[0:5000]

fig = rotor.plot(ax=axes[2], grid=True, logy=True, title="Power distribution")
```


Figure 33: Rotation speed, rotor angles, and power distributions

4.7. Simulating noise generation and propagation

Finally, the integrated simulation system allows simulating and generating the noise, each wind turbine produces. Figure 34 shows the input parameters of the noise model, with a single wind turbine WT1. The data binding contains references to the relevant 3D mean flow fields that were generated by the park model.

Noise Generation and Propagation

Models

```
noise_model_params = {
  "WT1":
    {
      "turbineType": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["turbineType"],
      "position": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["baseLocation"],
      "yaw": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["NacYaw"],
      "rpm": park_input_params["turbineArray"]["turbine1"]["RotSpeed"]
    }
}

store_input_parameters(noise_model_params, workspace_registry[workflow_steps[3]] )
```

Figure 34: Input parameters of the noise simulation

Figure 35 shows the standardized program interface that invokes the execution of the noise-simulating container.

```

client.containers.run(
    container_registry[workflow_steps[3]],
    "bash runAll.sh",
    auto_remove=True,
    volumes = data_binding[workflow_steps[3]],
    working_dir="/home/noise")

```

Figure 35: Program interface that invokes the execution of the STARCCM+ container

The noise fields, simulated by this container are stored as VTP files, which we now can parse and visualize by using the `K3D` and `VTK` libraries used in the `py_upwards` framework. Figure 36 shows the 3D rendering of such noise fields.

```

# render hub
reader.SetFileName(project_folder+'/hub_mast.stl')
reader.Update()
mast = k3d.vtk_poly_data(reader.GetOutput(), color=0xA9A9A9)
plot += mast

# render sound field
reader_vtp.SetFileName(project_folder+'/spp_db.vtp')
reader_vtp.Update()
sound = k3d.vtk_poly_data(reader_vtp.GetOutput(), color_attribute=('spp', 50, 57))
plot += sound

plot.display()

```


Figure 36: Visual noise propagation of the simulated wind turbine

After visualizing noise fields, the simulation workbench allows us to perform an audio synthesis of the noise that is generated by the wind turbine. The noise simulation created an audio file, which we can load and play by using standard audio capabilities of the Browser. Figure 37 shows the result.

Sound synthesis

```

sound_result = os.getcwd()+"/"+project_folder+"data/output/MonoSignal_3Blades.wav"
wavPlayer(sound_result)

```


Figure 37: Acoustic noise synthesis of a wind turbine

To summarize, the End-to-End example presented a walk through a complete wind park simulation.

1. It started with a fluid flow simulation in atmospheric-scale,
2. followed by a definition of a wind park, such that
3. a fluid flow simulation in neighbourhood-scale of turbines can be performed.
4. Resulting flow fields are used to investigate and simulate time series of wind turbine conditions such as the production of energy.
5. Finally, we presented results of the noise simulation and audio synthesis.

5. Conclusions

In this report, we documented the demonstrator of the serial integrated simulation system delivered to partners of the Upwards consortium. This documentation provides explanation to all components used to implement this serial integrated simulation platform. It explained the concept of the workflow underpinning the concept of Upwards to combine physical simulation systems. It provides insights into involved models and parameters and the systems that use these models to simulate physical behaviours of wind parks and turbines.

Furthermore, this report describes the technical foundations to encapsulate used simulation systems in software containers. It presents conventions made to create standard application interfaces to initialize and run simulations and data exchange interfaces between involved systems.

Finally, a guiding example shows the overall simulation setup of a virtual wind park located in Østerild, Denmark.

Partners of the Upwards consortium access the platform by using the Gitlab collaboration platform hosted by Fraunhofer ITWM (<https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards>).